

TPR-TOTAL PHYSICAL RESPONSE METHOD IN INCLUSIVE CLASSROOM "BABIES DON'T LEARN BY MEMORIZING LISTS; WHY SHOULD CHILDREN OR ADULTS?"

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Abstract. *The article illustrates data about the teaching method TPR, it`s stages of forming, advantages, discusses it`s weaknesses and the suitable position of its usage in practice.*

Key words: *teaching, new language, teaching techniques, silent period, commands, language - body conversation.*

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada TPR o'qitish metodikasi, uning shakllanish bosqichlari, afzalliklari, uning zaif tomonlari va amaliyotda qo'llanilishining to'g'ri pozitsiyasi haqida ma'lumotlar ko'rsatilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *o'qitish, yangi til, o'qitish texnikasi, jim davr, buyruqlar, til-tana suhbatı.*

Аннотация: *В статье иллюстрируются данные о методе обучения ТПР, его этапах формирования, преимуществах, обсуждаются его слабые стороны и целесообразность использования его на практике.*

Ключевые слова: *обучение, новый язык, приемы обучения, период молчания, команды, языково-телесный разговор.*

Methods of teaching a new language vary according to the learners` position, level, goal and degree. Teaching a language has different ways and paradigms. The effective methods of teaching English are The Direct Method, The Audio-Lingual Method, Suggestopedia, The Silent Way, Total Physical Response and it differs from person to person. In the history of teaching languages, there are many teaching approaches and techniques, with some being more well-known and successful than others. [1] Total physical response method is one of the methods of great importance in acquiring the new language.

Dr. James J. Asher originated the Total Physical Response approach to second language acquisition which is known internationally as **TPR**. Asher wanted to select a problem that was complex and could be applied to the real world.

Research work

He chose foreign language because

- it was a complex problem in skill learning
- most other psychologists abandoned research in FL because it was tough to get clean results, therefore meaning there was little competition for financial support.

“Zamanagóy til biliminiń kommunikatív-pragmatikalıq máseleleri hám shet tillerin oqıtıwdıń innovaciyalıq usılları”

Xalıqaralıq ilimiy-ámeliy konferenciya

This game is perfect for all levels, as even students who do not initially understand the game can catch on quickly. It can also be used for more advanced vocabulary and can be done at any pace to test quick understanding.

“Charades” is a helpful game for any learner, not just for language learning. Charades involves a student getting up and performing for the rest of the class. They are told a vocabulary word or action that the rest of the class needs to say, and then it’s their job to get that answer from the class. This helps test the student performer ability as well as the ability of the class.

You can also let your students get a little competitive by dividing them into teams. Teams alternate turns, so they can’t guess off of the other performer’s actions. This helps get your students more involved in the game, as everyone likes a little competition.

You can do this game with or without preparation, making it a great cool down activity or quick review game. If you want to prepare, write down your vocabulary (this works best with verbs) and put them on pieces of paper in a jar for your students to pull from. If you’re winging it, tell only the student that is performing which action they need to do.[4]

Overall, incorporating games like Simple Simon Says and Charades into language lessons offers a fun and effective way to engage students, reinforce learning, and develop essential communication skills. These activities cater to diverse learning styles and can be easily adapted to different levels and classroom settings.

Language learning can be challenging, but that doesn’t mean it has to be boring or tedious. TPR is a versatile and effective language teaching approach that can benefit students of all ages and proficiency levels. By incorporating gestures, actions and real-life scenarios into their practice, teachers can create engaging and enjoyable language lessons that both promote comprehension / retention and bring some joy to language learning.

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